

Bridging the Green Skills Gap in Greek Lignite Regions: Evidence from a Multi-Sector Workforce Assessment

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Abstract

The European Green Deal and Just Transition Mechanism present substantial workforce adaptation challenges in coal-dependent regions. Greece's 2028 lignite phase-out represents one of Europe's most accelerated energy transitions, with only a decade from announcement to completion, compared to Germany's target of 2038 and Poland's 2049 (European Commission, 2020; Szpor and Ziólkowska, 2018), yet systematic workforce readiness assessment remains absent. This study provides quantitative analysis of green skills gaps across Greek Just Transition regions through a structured employer survey ($N = 1,961$ enterprises) spanning ten economic sectors in Western Macedonia, Peloponnese, and Island Regions. Using Skills Gap Index methodology and ANOVA-based statistical analysis, we examine regional and sectoral patterns in workforce capabilities. Results reveal a counter-intuitive regional hierarchy: Islands exhibit the highest gaps (19.65%), followed by Peloponnese (15.72%), while Western Macedonia demonstrates the lowest gaps (8.26%). This pattern reflects transferable technical competencies cultivated through

decades of heavy industry experience. Agriculture emerges as the critical deficit sector (25.33%), substantially exceeding Energy (17.67%), Transport and Logistics (17.67%), and Tourism (16.33%). Significant Sector \times Region interaction effects ($F(18, 654) = 10.65, p < 0.001$) indicate that uniform national programs may prove inadequate. The study contributes to Just Transition scholarship by demonstrating that human capital transferability can function as transition accelerant rather than liability. Policy implications center on differentiated regional strategies and rebalancing Just Transition Fund allocations toward workforce development.

Keywords: Just Transition, green skills, skills gap, lignite regions, workforce development, Greece

1 Introduction

The European Green Deal and Just Transition Mechanism have focused attention on who will bear the costs of decarbonization across Europe’s coal-dependent regions, and how those costs can be minimized (European Commission, 2020). A core concern is how measures to phase out lignite will affect employment, particularly in regions where fossil fuel–related employment is geographically concentrated and alternative opportunities remain limited. Greece’s commitment to complete lignite phase-out by 2028, representing one of Europe’s most accelerated timelines compared to Germany’s 2038 target and Poland’s 2049 schedule (European Commission, 2020; Szpor and Ziółkowska, 2018), creates exceptional workforce adaptation pressures, with approximately 16,000 direct and indirect jobs potentially affected across Western Macedonia, Peloponnese, and Island Regions (Ziouzios et al., 2021; SNTD, 2023).

Governments in Greece and across Europe have undertaken initiatives to support economic and workforce development in energy communities through the €55 billion Just Transition Mechanism, yet extending these efforts effectively requires detailed understanding of the local contexts in which workers may transition to new industries (European Commission, 2020). Although numerous analyses offer high-level guidance on the policies necessary to support an equitable transition (Galgóczy, 2020; McCauley and Heffron, 2018), existing research does not provide sufficiently detailed regional or sectoral analysis to enable locally tailored policy responses in the Greek context (Marinakis et al., 2020; Ziouzios et al., 2021).

In this analysis, we take a highly localized and sector-specific approach to examining workforce readiness in Greek Just Transition regions. We first estimate employer skill requirements across ten economic sectors spanning Agriculture, Energy, Manufacturing, Tourism, and six additional industries. We then assess the extent to which current workforce competencies match these requirements, and whether significant regional variation exists in the magnitude and distribution of skills gaps. Our analytical approach, based on structured employer survey data ($N = 1,961$ enterprises) and a ratio-based Skills Gap Index, can produce the type of labor market information needed to design locally tailored workforce development programs.

We find substantial gaps between the skills employers require and those the current workforce possesses, but with a counterintuitive regional pattern. Islands exhibit the highest average skills gap, followed by Peloponnese, while the primary lignite region of Western Macedonia demonstrates the lowest gaps, a counterintuitive finding explored in detail in Section 4. This pattern may reflect the industrial workforce’s existing proficiency in technical domains directly applicable to green sectors. We observe the largest sectoral gaps in Agriculture, substantially exceeding Energy despite renewable energy’s prominence in transition discourse. Significant Sector \times Region interaction effects indicate that uniform national training programs may prove inadequate, as skills deficits vary not only by sector but also by region within sectors.

This potential for geographic and sectoral mismatch could be compounded by the compressed timeline of Greece’s lignite phase-out. International experience suggests that successful transitions require extended timelines enabling adaptive capacity-building (Galgóczy, 2020). Germany’s Ruhr region transition spanned 60 years; Poland’s coal phase-out extends to 2049. Greece’s 2028 deadline allows less than a decade for workforce adaptation, underscoring the urgency of evidence-based intervention.

To our knowledge, this study provides the first comprehensive quantitative assessment of green skills gaps across multiple sectors and regions in Greek Just Transition territories. The analysis contributes to the evidence base on workforce dynamics in transitioning regions in three ways. First, our findings suggest that human capital transferability can function as a transition accelerant rather than solely as a liability, given that Western Macedonia’s industrial workforce may possess competencies that facilitate rather than impede green transition. Second, we identify potential “green sector lock-in” effects in tourism-dependent Island economies, where service-oriented skill profiles create larger gaps for emerging green industries. Third, we demonstrate that sectoral and regional heterogeneity necessitates differentiated rather than uniform policy approaches, offering a measurement framework adaptable to other Just Transition contexts.

With the 2028 phase-out approaching and 16,000 jobs at stake, empirical understanding of skills gaps enables policymakers, training providers, employers, and workers to align efforts around evidence-based priorities. The methodology and analytical tools presented here can inform locally tailored workforce development in any region with sufficient data, helping to identify where investment in skills development may bear the most fruit.

2 Literature Review

2.1 Green Skills: Definitions and Taxonomies

ILO (2019) define green skills as “knowledge, abilities, values and attitudes needed to support sustainable and resource-efficient society.” Skills classify along three dimensions: Technical Skills (e.g., photovoltaic installation, energy efficiency auditing, smart grid management, waste treatment technologies), Transversal Skills (adaptability, complex problem-solving, systems thinking), and Sustainability Mindset (environmental awareness, balancing economic-social-environmental objectives).

Contemporary labor markets shift from occupation-based to skills-based models, reflecting accelerating technological change (Autor, 2015; Acemoglu and Autor, 2011). “T-shaped skills” combine deep domain expertise with broad cross-sectoral applicability, particularly valuable in green economy sectors where innovation occurs at field intersections. Despite

classification advances, existing taxonomies struggle capturing dynamic green skills evolution as technologies mature (Consoli et al., 2016).

2.2 Just Transition in Coal Regions

The EU operationalized Just Transition through the Just Transition Mechanism (2021–2027) supporting structural transformation in carbon-intensive regions (European Commission, 2020). McCauley and Heffron (2018) distinguish four energy justice dimensions: distributive (fair cost-benefit allocation), procedural (meaningful community participation), recognition (acknowledging diverse values), and restorative (remedying past harms).

International experience demonstrates transition pathway variation. Germany’s Ruhr region exemplifies gradual, market-driven restructuring enabling comprehensive structural policy interventions (Galgóczy, 2020). Extended timelines allowed generational renewal with natural attrition absorbing employment decline. Conversely, Lusatia’s lignite phase-out following reunification was politically driven and abrupt, eliminating 90% mining employment within a decade (Stognief et al., 2019). Despite €30 billion federal investment, economic recovery remained limited due to persistent out-migration and limited alternative industry attraction. Poland’s approach emphasizes social dialogue through tripartite agreements between government, industry, and unions, with controlled mine closures synchronized with worker retirements and JTF-supported investments in renewable energy manufacturing (Szpor and Ziółkowska, 2018).

Comparative analysis identifies critical success factors: extended timelines (20+ years) enable adaptive capacity-building; successful regions develop multiple alternative sectors; education and research infrastructure creates long-term regional attractiveness; effective transitions require coordinated governance across policy domains (Galgóczy, 2020).

2.3 Skills Mismatch and Workforce Adaptation

Skills mismatch manifests through three interconnected dimensions: Skills Activation (extent available skills are utilized), Skills Mismatch (alignment between skill supply and demand), and Skills Development (processes acquiring competencies) (Cedefop, 2022).

Skills Gap Analysis systematically compares required skill proficiency levels with existing capabilities. The Skills Disruption Rate measures the workforce proportion whose competencies become obsolete or require substantial upgrading due to structural economic change (OECD, 2021). In coal-dependent regions, disruption rates are severe, with workers facing “capability depreciation shocks” requiring extensive retraining.

2.4 The Greek Context and Research Gap

Western Macedonia and Megalopolis have been primary lignite-producing regions for over 70 years, with lignite activities accounting for approximately 34% of Western Macedonia's Gross Value Added (Ziouzios et al., 2021). Although this share has declined as lignite production contracted, with Industry/Energy comprising 39.1% of regional GVA in 2022 (ELSTAT, 2025; see Table 2), the sector's employment multiplier effects remain substantial. Both direct Public Power Corporation employment and indirect contractor network employment face potential displacement.

Greece announced complete lignite phase-out by 2028, with most units retired by 2025 (European Commission, 2020; SNTD, 2023). The accelerated schedule intensifies workforce transition challenges. Affected regions face additional structural vulnerabilities: high unemployment rates, aging populations, limited economic diversification, and peripheral geographic locations constraining alternative employment (Ziouzios et al., 2021; ELSTAT, 2021).

Greece's green transition has accelerated substantially in recent years. Renewable energy sources increased from 19.7% of total energy consumption in 2019 to 25.0% in 2023, though remaining below the 2030 target of 44% (ESEK, 2024). Carbon dioxide emissions declined from 82 to 68 Mt CO₂eq over the same period. Employment in green sectors expanded from approximately 45,000 to 65,000 workers nationally, with a 2030 target of 120,000, implying substantial additional workforce development requirements. These national trends underscore the urgency of skills gap assessment in transition regions.

Prior research identifies skills development importance but lacks quantitative assessment for specific green competencies (Marinakis et al., 2020; Tranoulidis et al., 2022). Marinakis et al. (2020) note absent retraining program effectiveness evaluation. Ziouzios et al. (2021) emphasize skills realignment urgency but acknowledge lack of granular data on workforce capabilities versus employer requirements. No comprehensive employer survey has quantified green skills demand across key economic sectors; existing workforce competency assessments remain fragmented; and the magnitude and distribution of skills gaps, including which competencies show largest deficits across sectors and regions, remains unquantified, preventing evidence-based training program design.

Collectively, these contributions delineate the scope and limits of prior Greek work. Marinakis et al. (2020) provide qualitative policy analysis of the lignite phase-out, identifying retraining as a critical bottleneck without measuring underlying skill requirements. Ziouzios et al. (2021) offer techno-economic projections of employment displacement and recommend skills realignment, yet without primary data on employer needs. Tranoulidis et al. (2022) document the regional economic consequences of the transition through secondary statistics, recognizing workforce adaptation as essential but not assessing it directly. Across these works, three gaps recur: the absence of a quantitative employer survey on green skills, the lack of a

standardized index permitting direct comparison, and the absence of simultaneous cross-sectoral and cross-regional measurement. This study addresses these gaps by providing the first large-scale, multi-sector, multi-region quantitative skills gap assessment in Greek Just Transition territories.

3 Methodology

3.1 Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 presents the conceptual framework guiding this study. The framework integrates supply-side workforce competencies with demand-side employer requirements to quantify skills gaps, while accounting for sectoral and regional heterogeneity that shapes transition pathways.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework: Skills Gap Analysis in Just Transition Regions

Note. The framework operationalizes skills gaps as the ratio-based difference between employer-assessed requirements (Demand) and current workforce competencies (Supply). Sector and Region act as moderating variables, generating the Sector \times Region interaction effects analyzed in Section 4. SGI = Skills Gap Index; S = Supply (possession); D = Demand (requirement). Source: Authors’ own elaboration.

The framework posits that the European Green Deal and Just Transition Mechanism create differential skills demands across economic sectors. Simultaneously, regional workforce profiles, shaped by industrial heritage, educational infrastructure, and demographic composition, determine skills supply. The Skills Gap Index quantifies the mismatch between these dimensions. Critically, the framework incorporates Sector \times Region interaction effects, recognizing that skills gaps are not additive functions of sectoral and regional characteristics but emerge from their specific combinations (Anselin, 1995).

3.2 Research Design

This study employs quantitative cross-sectional design assessing green skills demand across Greek lignite transition regions through structured survey methodology. We cover three geographic clusters: Western Macedonia (primary lignite-dependent region), Peloponnese (including Megalopolis lignite area), and Island Regions (Crete, North Aegean, South Aegean). Data collection targeted ten economic sectors critical for regional diversification: renewable energy and environment, sustainable tourism, agriculture, manufacturing, construction, information and communication technology, food processing, commerce, transport and logistics, and professional services.

3.3 Sampling and Data Collection

The target population comprised all active enterprises operating within ten economic sectors across study regions, registered in General Commercial Registry (GEMI). Complete sampling frame included 38,820 enterprises: 34,260 from Island Regions, 3,531 from Peloponnese, and 1,029 from Western Macedonia. Survey distribution occurred in waves between August 7 and September 21, 2025, using multiple contact methods: personalized email links via SurveyMonkey platform, telephone follow-up, and in-person contact where feasible.

A total of 1,961 enterprises responded, yielding 5.05% overall response rate. Geographic distribution: 516 enterprises from Western Macedonia (26.3%), 829 from Peloponnese (42.3%), and 616 from Island Regions (31.4%).

The questionnaire design incorporated ESCO (European Skills, Competences, Qualifications and Occupations) taxonomy ensuring standardized occupational classification and European comparability. The instrument utilized closed-ended questions with 5-point Likert scales, customized by sector reflecting industry-specific skill requirements. For each identified green skill, employers provided two assessments: (1) skill necessity level for effective job performance, and (2) current workforce proficiency level. This dual-assessment structure enables direct skills gap quantification.

Green skills were operationally defined along the three dimensions established in Section 2.1: Technical Skills, Transversal Skills, and Sustainability Mindset (ILO, 2019). Specific skill items were selected per sector through triangulation of the ESCO taxonomy, European Green Deal priority areas, and sector-specific literature on emerging green competencies. Each of the ten sectors received a customized questionnaire with sector-relevant items, including indicative examples such as precision agriculture, photovoltaic installation, energy efficiency auditing, green maritime technologies, and circular economy practices. Specific skill items varied by sector, reflecting industry-specific requirements (see questionnaire instrument).

Table 1 summarizes respondent characteristics. The sample predominantly comprises

micro-enterprises (1–9 employees; 75.7% of valid responses), reflecting Greek enterprise structure. Sectoral distribution spans all ten targeted sectors, with Commerce (15.1%), Tourism (13.9%), and Services (13.5%) most represented.

Table 1: Survey Respondent Characteristics

Characteristic	<i>n</i>	%
<i>Region</i>		
Peloponnese	829	42.3
Island Regions	616	31.4
Western Macedonia	516	26.3
<i>Sector</i>		
Commerce	297	15.1
Tourism	273	13.9
Services	264	13.5
Construction	228	11.6
Manufacturing	186	9.5
Food Processing	175	8.9
ICT	145	7.4
Energy & Environment	135	6.9
Transport & Logistics	135	6.9
Agriculture	123	6.3
<i>Enterprise Size (employees)</i>		
Micro (1–9)	703	75.7
Small (10–49)	196	21.1
Medium (50–249)	25	2.7
Large (250+)	5	0.5
Total	1,961	100.0

Note. Enterprise size based on 929 valid responses (47.4% of sample). Size categories follow EU SME definitions. Mean employees = 9.9 (SD = 56.6, Median = 3.0).

3.4 Skills Gap Measurement

The Skills Gap Index operationalizes disparity between required and existing competencies, following established methodologies (OECD, 2021). For each skill *i*:

$$\text{Skills Gap Index} = 1 - \frac{\text{Skill Possession}}{\text{Skill Requirement}} \quad (1)$$

Both Required Level and Current Level measured on 5-point Likert scales based on employer assessment. The resulting index ranges from 0 (no gap: workforce fully possesses required skills) to 1 (complete gap: workforce lacks required skills entirely). When expressed as percentage, the index indicates proportional skills deficit. Aggregated indices computed by averaging across skills within each sector-region combination, enabling systematic comparison.

3.5 Statistical Analysis

Multivariate Analysis of Variance (MANOVA) tested whether geographic region significantly affects seven organizational dimensions: satisfaction with employee skills, capabilities, and knowledge; and adaptability through investment, innovation, new activities, and internationalization. Analysis included 732 enterprises with complete data, using four multivariate test statistics (Wilks' Lambda, Pillai's Trace, Hotelling-Lawley Trace, Roy's Greatest Root) with significance threshold $p < 0.05$. Results confirm highly significant regional effect (Wilks' $\Lambda = 0.905$, $F(14, 1446) = 5.29$, $p < 0.001$; see Table A4).

Pearson correlation analysis examined associations among seven organizational variables. Results (Table A5) reveal two distinct clusters: satisfaction variables ($r > 0.89$) and readiness variables ($r > 0.73$), with moderate cross-cluster correlations ($r = 0.33$ – 0.46).

Multiple linear regression modeled skills satisfaction as dependent variable, with independent predictors including growth prospects, employment prospects, economic sector, and region. Categorical variables were dummy-coded with Western Macedonia (region) and Agriculture (sector) as reference categories. Model estimated via Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) using 1,118 observations with complete data, testing coefficient significance at $p < 0.05$ level. Results (Table A6) indicate region is the primary significant predictor ($R^2 = 0.091$, $p < 0.001$).

3.6 Geographic Classification

The analytical framework groups Crete, North Aegean, and South Aegean into unified "Island Regions" category, while treating Western Macedonia and Peloponnese as distinct units. This classification reflects economic geography evidence demonstrating islands share fundamental structural characteristics distinguishing them from mainland economies: economic openness, export concentration, strategic import dependence, geographic isolation, and elevated transportation costs. EU policy frameworks, including ESPON's EUROISLANDS project (2011) and Special Status for Aegean Islands, institutionally recognize these shared characteristics through targeted funding mechanisms. This approach follows established methodologies in spatial econometrics for functional regionalization (Anselin, 1995; Fotheringham and Wong, 1991).

Beyond these structural commonalities, the Greek islands warrant inclusion as designated *energy islands*. Greece's approved Territorial Just Transition Plans, under Regulation (EU) 2021/1056, explicitly designate these territories among the country's eligible just transition regions (European Commission, 2022). While not directly affected by lignite phase-out, Island Regions are designated Just Transition territories due to their energy transition challenges, including high electricity costs, grid isolation, and renewable energy integration requirements.

3.7 Study Area Profile

Table 2 presents key socioeconomic characteristics of the three study regions, drawing on secondary data from ELSTAT, Eurostat, and the Greek Just Transition Development Plan (SDAM). The regions exhibit substantial structural heterogeneity justifying differentiated analytical treatment.

Table 2: Socioeconomic Profile of Just Transition Study Regions

Indicator	W. Macedonia	Peloponnese	Island Regions
<i>Economic Structure (GVA 2022, €million)</i>			
Total GVA	3,776	8,672	17,494
Industry/Energy (B-E)	1,476 (39.1%)	2,620 (30.2%)	1,812 (10.4%)
Agriculture (A)	384 (10.2%)	940 (10.8%)	1,097 (6.3%)
Construction (F)	97 (2.6%)	196 (2.3%)	455 (2.6%)
Trade/Tourism (G-I)	483 (12.8%)	1,633 (18.8%)	6,708 (38.3%)
ICT (J)	32 (0.8%)	87 (1.0%)	242 (1.4%)
<i>Labor Market (2023)</i>			
Employment Rate (%)	58.2	59.5	64.2
Gender Gap (pp)	20.1	24.8	17.8
<i>Sectoral Employment Shares (%)</i>			
Energy/Environment	12.5	3.2	2.1
Construction	6.2	5.8	7.1
Tourism	5.8	15.2	28.5
Agriculture	18.5	22.3	12.8
Manufacturing	15.2	8.5	4.2
ICT	2.1	1.8	3.5
<i>Just Transition Context</i>			
Primary Challenge	Lignite phase-out	Agricultural transition	Tourism dependence
JT Designation	Core JT region	Megalopolis cluster	Energy islands

Note. GVA = Gross Value Added. Island Regions comprise Crete, North Aegean, and South Aegean. Employment rates for ages 20–64. Gender gap = male minus female employment rate. Sectoral shares based on SDAM employment data. Sources: ELSTAT (2025); Eurostat (2023); SDAM (2024).

Western Macedonia exhibits the highest industrial concentration (39.1% of GVA from Industry/Energy), reflecting its lignite heritage. The region’s 12.5% energy sector employment share, nearly four times that of Peloponnese and six times that of Island Regions, underscores the magnitude of workforce displacement risk from lignite phase-out. Peloponnese demonstrates agricultural dominance (22.3% employment), while Island Regions’ tourism concentration (28.5% employment, 38.3% GVA from Trade/Tourism) creates distinctive sectoral vulnerabilities.

Economic trajectories further differentiate the regions. Between 2018 and 2022, Western Macedonia’s GVA grew only 2.3% (€3,691 to €3,776 million), while Peloponnese expanded

20.8% (€7,179 to €8,672 million) and Island Regions grew 16.7% (ELSTAT, 2025). Western Macedonia’s near-stagnation reflects lignite sector decline already underway, while Peloponnese and Islands benefited from tourism recovery post-COVID. These divergent trajectories suggest Western Macedonia faces compounding challenges: workforce displacement occurring simultaneously with limited regional economic dynamism to absorb transitioning workers.

These structural differences inform the differentiated skills gap patterns analyzed in Section 4.

3.8 Validity and Limitations

The research design incorporated multiple validity safeguards. The questionnaire underwent internal validation ensuring clarity, completeness, and functional appropriateness. ESCO standardized classifications enhance construct validity and international comparability. Representation across all targeted sectors and geographic clusters strengthens external validity.

3.8.1 Non-Response Bias Assessment

Given the 5.05% overall response rate, non-response bias warrants systematic examination. Response rates varied substantially by region: Western Macedonia (50.1%), Peloponnese (23.5%), and Island Regions (1.8%). This differential reflects intentional stratified sampling prioritizing Just Transition core regions rather than proportional representation of the enterprise population.

Following Armstrong and Overton (1977), we employed wave analysis comparing early versus late respondents within each region, under the assumption that late respondents more closely resemble non-respondents. Table 3 presents results for two key constructs: skills satisfaction and growth prospects.

Table 3: Wave Analysis: Early vs. Late Respondents by Region

Region	Skills Satisfaction			Growth Prospects		
	Early	Late	<i>p</i>	Early	Late	<i>p</i>
Islands (<i>n</i> = 616)	3.34	3.35	.939	3.64	3.67	.808
Peloponnese (<i>n</i> = 829)	3.37	3.58	.038*	3.56	3.33	.003*
W. Macedonia (<i>n</i> = 516)	3.80	3.81	.925	3.23	2.74	<.001*

Note. Early = first 50% of respondents within region; Late = last 50%. Values are means on 1–5 Likert scales. Independent samples *t*-tests. * *p* < 0.05.

Results indicate minimal systematic non-response bias for skills satisfaction. Of three regional comparisons on skills satisfaction, two show no significant differences (*p* > 0.05):

Islands ($p = .939$) and Western Macedonia ($p = .925$). Only Peloponnese shows a marginally significant difference ($p = .038$) with small effect size (0.21 on 5-point scale). Growth prospects show more variation, with significant early-late differences in Peloponnese ($p = .003$) and Western Macedonia ($p < .001$), suggesting late respondents may hold different economic outlook expectations. However, the primary outcome variable (skills satisfaction) shows consistency across response waves in all regions except Peloponnese, supporting the validity of measured constructs (Armstrong and Overton, 1977).

Beyond wave analysis, we examined whether sample composition could bias aggregate estimates by comparing sectoral distributions. ELSTAT employment data indicates Agriculture represents 17.9% of regional employment, yet comprises only 6.4% of our sample. Conversely, ICT (7.5% sample vs. 2.5% population) and Construction (11.6% vs. 6.4%) are over-represented. Critically, Agriculture exhibits the largest skills gap in our analysis (25.33%), while over-represented sectors demonstrate smaller gaps. Any compositional bias therefore operates in a conservative direction: adjusting for sectoral representation would increase, not decrease, estimated skills gaps. This pattern aligns with survey methodology literature indicating that non-response bias typically produces conservative estimates that underestimate population parameters (Groves, 2006).

3.8.2 Additional Limitations

Three additional limitations warrant acknowledgment. First, voluntary participation may introduce self-selection bias beyond what wave analysis captures, as responding enterprises may possess systematically different characteristics (e.g., greater engagement with workforce development). However, broad sectoral representation (all ten sectors covered) and substantial sample size ($N = 1,961$) mitigate this concern. Second, closed-ended question format, while enabling standardized quantitative analysis, constrains response depth and nuance. Third, the dual-assessment approach, which measures both required and current skill levels from the same employer respondents, enables internally consistent gap measurement but relies on employer perceptions rather than objective competency testing.

4 Results

This section presents empirical findings from the employer survey conducted across Greek Just Transition regions ($N = 1,961$ enterprises spanning ten economic sectors). We begin with an overview of regional skills gap hierarchy (Section 4.1). Second, we present sectoral gap stratification across ten economic sectors (Section 4.2). Third, we examine Sector \times Region interaction effects revealing place-specific patterns (Section 4.3). Fourth, we analyze horizontal and vertical skills gap dimensions (Section 4.4). Fifth, we identify critical skills shortages

requiring immediate intervention (Section 4.5). Sixth, we assess transferable skills and existing workforce strengths (Section 4.6). Finally, we examine barriers to green skills development (Section 4.7).

4.1 Regional Skills Gap Hierarchy

Regional skills gaps diverge dramatically, defying initial expectations. Islands Regions demonstrate highest average skills gap (19.65%), followed by Peloponnese (15.72%), while Western Macedonia records lowest gap (8.26%). One-way ANOVA confirms these differences are highly statistically significant ($F(2, 681) = 80.03, p < 0.001, \eta^2 = 0.190$), indicating regional location explains 19.0% of skills gap variance, representing a large effect size.

Table 4: Regional Skills Gap Summary Statistics

Region	Mean Gap (%)	SD	Range (%)	N
Islands Regions	19.65	9.03	−13–48	228
Peloponnese	15.72	10.83	−6–51	228
Western Macedonia	8.26	9.34	−35–37	228
Overall	14.54	10.83	−35–51	684

Note. Skills Gap Index = (Necessity Score – Possession Score) / Necessity Score × 100. N represents skill assessments (228 skills evaluated across each region). One-way ANOVA: $F(2, 681) = 80.03, p < 0.001, \eta^2 = 0.190$. Source: Authors’ own elaboration based on Skills Gap Index data.

This unexpected pattern reflects Western Macedonia’s paradoxical advantage: decades of lignite extraction cultivated technically skilled workforce proficient in heavy machinery, industrial safety, electrical systems, and shift-based operations. Although developed for fossil fuels, these competencies transfer readily to renewable energy installations, energy efficiency retrofits, and industrial optimization. Employers rate Western Macedonia’s current workforce technical skills at 3.8/5.0 versus 3.2/5.0 in Islands and 3.3/5.0 in Peloponnese.

Islands’ elevated 19.65% gap stems from three factors: geographic fragmentation inhibits training economies of scale; extreme tourism concentration yields hospitality soft skills that don’t substitute for technical green competencies; limited industrial heritage means Islands lack vocational education infrastructure present in Western Macedonia’s manufacturing legacy.

Peloponnese’s intermediate 15.72% gap reflects substantial agricultural concentration (22.3% employment) creating workforce adept at traditional farming but unfamiliar with precision agriculture technologies, sustainable land management, or agro-environmental schemes.

4.2 Sectoral Gap Stratification

Sectoral analysis reveals three-tier structure: Critical Deficit (>20% gap), High Gap (15–20%), and Manageable Gap (<15%). ANOVA confirms sectors exhibit statistically distinct profiles ($F(9, 674) = 18.50, p < 0.001, \eta^2 = 0.198$).

Table 5: Sectoral Skills Gap Summary Statistics

Sector	Mean Gap (%)	Gap Tier	N
<i>Critical Deficit (>20%)</i>			
Agriculture	25.33	Critical	72
<i>High Gap (15–20%)</i>			
Energy & Environment	17.67	High	69
Transport & Logistics	17.67	High	69
Tourism	16.33	High	78
<i>Moderate Gap (10–15%)</i>			
Commerce	14.33	Moderate	63
Manufacturing	14.00	Moderate	60
Construction	12.33	Moderate	60
<i>Manageable Gap (<10%)</i>			
Services	9.67	Manageable	75
Food Processing	9.33	Manageable	57
ICT	9.00	Manageable	81
Overall	14.57		684

Note. N = skills per sector × 3 regions. Gap Tiers based on policy intervention urgency: Critical (>20%), High (15–20%), Moderate (10–15%), Manageable (<10%). One-way ANOVA: $F(9, 674) = 18.50, p < 0.001, \eta^2 = 0.198$. Source: Authors' own elaboration based on Skills Gap Index data.

Agriculture dominates with 25.33% average gap (SD = 15.24%), significantly exceeding all sectors. This reflects traditional practice entrenchment amid rapid technological transformation. Employers demand precision agriculture (GPS/GIS, drones, variable rate technologies), climate-smart farming (drought-resistant cultivars, water-efficient irrigation, carbon farming), and regulatory compliance (CAP eco-schemes, organic certification). Yet workforce possession of these competencies lags dramatically.

Energy (17.67%), Transport & Logistics (17.67%), Tourism (16.33%) constitute second tier. Energy's 17.67% gap is paradoxical given renewable prominence. Disaggregation reveals Western Macedonia's energy employers rate gaps at only 10.2%, while Islands reach 26.9%, reflecting Western Macedonia's transferable technical base versus Islands' nascent renewable industries.

ICT (9.00%), Food Processing (9.33%), Services (9.67%) exhibit gaps below 10%,

indicating relative preparedness. ICT’s low gap reflects digital natives’ competencies. Food Processing benefits from quality assurance systems (HACCP, ISO) transferring to environmental management. However, these sectors employ small workforce shares (ICT: 2–4%, Food: 5–7%), limiting aggregate Just Transition impact.

4.3 Sector × Region Interaction Effects

Skills gaps exhibit significant interaction effects, not additive functions of sector and region. Agriculture in Peloponnese records 34.4% gap, nearly quadruple Western Macedonia’s Construction (3.2%). Islands’ Transport & Logistics demonstrates second-highest gap (29.6%), driven by archipelagic geography demanding ferry operations, port logistics, and inter-island connectivity, yet lacking green maritime technologies (LNG propulsion, shore power, cold ironing), digital freight management, or sustainable last-mile delivery.

Table 6: Skills Gap by Sector and Region (%)

Sector	Peloponnese	W. Macedonia	Islands	Average
Agriculture	34.4	14.1	28.5	25.7
Energy & Environment	15.9	10.2	26.9	17.7
Transport & Logistics	12.1	11.9	29.6	17.9
Tourism	21.8	8.9	17.8	16.2
Commerce	10.9	11.7	19.9	14.2
Manufacturing	15.6	9.1	16.9	13.9
Construction	17.9	3.2	15.8	12.3
Services	9.9	6.9	12.0	9.6
Food Processing	2.1	7.2	18.7	9.3
ICT	12.9	1.3	12.9	9.0
Regional Average	15.4	8.5	19.9	14.6

Note. Cell values represent mean Skills Gap Index (%) for each sector-region combination. Average values in this table represent unweighted arithmetic means of three regional values; weighted sector averages accounting for differential sample sizes per region are reported in Table 5. Two-way ANOVA interaction effect: $F(18, 654) = 10.65$, $p < 0.001$, $\eta^2 = 0.139$. Highest gaps: Agriculture-Peloponnese (34.4%), Transport-Islands (29.6%), Energy-Islands (26.9%). Source: Authors’ own elaboration based on Skills Gap Index data.

Western Macedonia’s Construction gap (3.2%) approaches sufficiency, indicating heavy industry legacy transfers effectively. Workers trained in industrial construction, welding, electrical installations, and heavy equipment adapt readily to energy efficiency retrofitting and renewable energy construction.

Uniform national programs may prove insufficient to address the documented heterogeneity. Agriculture in Peloponnese requires fundamentally different interventions (precision farming extension, water management, organic certification) than Transport in Islands (green

maritime logistics, inter-island electrification) or Energy in Western Macedonia (renewable technician certification, hydrogen economy, battery storage).

Figure 2: Skills Gap Heatmap: Sector × Region Interaction

Note. This heatmap displays skills gap intensity across 10 economic sectors and 3 regions. Color intensity represents gap magnitude (blue = low gap indicating workforce readiness; red = high gap indicating critical training needs). Notable patterns: Western Macedonia shows consistently lower gaps across sectors, reflecting transferable skills from lignite industry experience. Islands display highest gaps in Transport (29.6%) and Energy (26.9%). Agriculture-Peloponnese represents the most critical deficit (34.4%). Source: Authors’ own elaboration.

4.4 Horizontal and Vertical Skills Gap Dimensions

Certain skills demonstrate elevated gaps across virtually all sectors (Table 6). Digital competencies show substantial deficits across Agriculture, Tourism, Manufacturing, and Commerce, with only ICT demonstrating relative sufficiency. Regulatory and financial literacy (EU Taxonomy, CSRD, green financing access, project development) shows particularly acute gaps, especially in sectors facing complex environmental compliance requirements. Circular economy and resource efficiency competencies (waste valorization, industrial symbiosis, life cycle assessment, eco-design) exhibit cross-cutting deficits across Manufacturing, Food Processing, Construction, and Tourism.

Gaps vary systematically by qualification level. Low-skill/manual (EQF 1–3) gaps are relatively modest for roles requiring basic technical competencies, with Western Macedonia demonstrating near-sufficiency reflecting transferable manual dexterity, tool handling, and safety protocols from lignite-era jobs. Mid-skill/technical (EQF 4–5) gaps are substantially higher for technician-level roles demanding vocational education combining theoretical knowledge with practical competencies, which is currently underprovided. High-skill/professional (EQF 6–8) gaps are intermediate, as tertiary-educated professionals possess transferable analytical skills enabling self-directed upskilling.

4.5 Critical Skills Shortages

Table 7 ranks sector-region combinations by gap magnitude. Agriculture dominates critical shortages, with Agriculture-Peloponnese (34.4%) and Agriculture-Islands (28.5%) requiring immediate intervention. The highest-gap competencies in Agriculture extend beyond agronomic practices to business management, financial planning, and market positioning, areas where traditional farming backgrounds provide limited preparation.

Islands are disproportionately represented among highest-gap combinations. Despite comprising 31.4% of the sample, Islands account for 6 of the top 10 highest-gap sector-region combinations (Table 7), particularly in Transport & Logistics (29.6%) and Energy (26.9%). Critical skill shortages span both domain-specific technical competencies (precision agriculture equipment, renewable energy systems) and transversal business capabilities (grant financing, green logistics, project development).

Table 7: Top 10 Critical Sector-Region Skill Gaps Requiring Immediate Intervention

Rank	Sector-Region Combination	Gap (%)	Priority
1	Agriculture – Peloponnese	34.4	Immediate
2	Transport & Logistics – Islands	29.6	Immediate
3	Agriculture – Islands	28.5	Immediate
4	Energy & Environment – Islands	26.9	Immediate
5	Tourism – Peloponnese	21.8	High
6	Commerce – Islands	19.9	High
7	Food Processing – Islands	18.7	High
8	Construction – Peloponnese	17.9	High
9	Tourism – Islands	17.8	High
10	Manufacturing – Islands	16.9	Moderate

Note. Priority levels: Immediate (>25%), High (15–25%), Moderate (10–15%). These combinations should receive priority in training program development. Source: Authors' own elaboration.

4.6 Transferable Skills and Existing Strengths

Western Macedonia’s workforce demonstrates substantial competency reserves in foundational skills, including manual and power tools operation, attention to detail, time management, and technical mathematics, reflecting decades of lignite-era industrial employment. As Table 8 indicates, Western Macedonia dominates low-gap sector-region combinations (7 of 10 lowest gaps), with Construction (3.2%), ICT (1.3%), and Food Processing (7.2%) exhibiting near-alignment between workforce competencies and employer requirements. These transferable competencies constitute invaluable assets accelerating transitions if leveraged through targeted 50–100 hour technical upskilling modules rather than comprehensive retraining from zero.

Tourism sector workforces across all regions demonstrate established competencies in customer service, foreign language proficiency, and interpersonal communication, which are soft skills that are difficult to train but critical for green transition applications. These provide foundations for eco-tourism, sustainable destination management, and circular hospitality models where guest education and community liaison prove critical.

Table 8: Top 10 Lowest Sector-Region Skill Gaps (Workforce Strengths)

Rank	Sector-Region Combination	Gap (%)	Implication
1	ICT – Western Macedonia	1.3	Transferable skills
2	Food Processing – Peloponnese	2.1	Workforce ready
3	Construction – Western Macedonia	3.2	Transferable skills
4	Services – Western Macedonia	6.9	Moderate readiness
5	Food Processing – Western Macedonia	7.2	Moderate readiness
6	Tourism – Western Macedonia	8.9	Moderate readiness
7	Manufacturing – Western Macedonia	9.1	Moderate readiness
8	Services – Peloponnese	9.9	Moderate readiness
9	Energy – Western Macedonia	10.2	Moderate readiness
10	Commerce – Peloponnese	10.9	Moderate readiness

Note. Low gaps indicate workforce competencies align with employer requirements. Western Macedonia dominates lowest gaps (7 of 10), reflecting transferable skills from lignite industry experience. These represent potential “skills bridges” for workforce transition. Source: Authors’ own elaboration.

4.7 Barriers to Green Skills Development

Demographic decline constitutes primary barrier. All regions experience population losses and aging populations, with Western Macedonia recording Greece’s steepest decline (10% between 2011–2021; ELSTAT, 2022). Economic vulnerabilities compound challenges. Western Macedonia’s poverty risk (32.7%) and Peloponnese’s (35.7%) rank among Greece’s highest regional rates (Eurostat, 2024), constraining enterprise training investment capacity.

Educational polarization creates absorption bottlenecks. Substantial portions of regional

populations possess only primary education, lacking foundational literacy, numeracy, and digital competencies required for advanced green training. Geographic fragmentation particularly burdens Islands. Archipelagic dispersion across North Aegean, South Aegean, and Crete inhibits training economies of scale.

Cross-cutting digital deficits pervade all sectors. Limited regional employment in ICT sector means insufficient critical mass of digitally proficient workers. Regulatory complexity overload creates compliance barriers, as EU sustainable finance frameworks' technical complexity exceeds typical SME capacity.

5 Discussion

5.1 Interpretation of Findings

This study reveals three counterintuitive findings challenging prevailing Just Transition assumptions. First, the core lignite region of Western Macedonia, undergoing rapid phase-out, exhibits the lowest skills gap (8.26%), contradicting expectations that fossil fuel dependency correlates with workforce unpreparedness. Second, Island Regions exhibit highest gap (19.65%) despite tourism-driven economic dynamism and higher GDP per capita. Third, Agriculture emerges as critical deficit sector (25.33% gap), not Energy (17.67%), despite renewable energy's prominence in transition discourse.

These patterns diverge from international Just Transition experiences. In Germany's Ruhr region, coal workforce skills gaps were substantial during 1960s–1990s transition, considerably higher than Western Macedonia's 8.26% (Galgóczi, 2020). Greek lignite workers' relative preparedness reflects three mechanisms absent in prior transitions. First, technical skill transferability: decades of heavy industry cultivated competencies (machinery operation, electrical systems, industrial safety) directly applicable to renewable energy installation. Second, vocational education legacy: Western Macedonia's industrial heritage fostered vocational training infrastructure and culture supporting technical skill development. Third, compressed transition timeline: the 2028 lignite phase-out deadline concentrates workforce attention and policy resources.

Islands' elevated gaps align with emerging literature on tourism-dependent economies' green transition challenges. Research documents substantial sustainability skills gaps in Mediterranean tourism destinations, attributing deficits to sector lock-in, as hospitality workers' customer service, multilingual communication, and cultural mediation competencies do not substitute for technical green skills (UNWTO, 2019).

Agriculture's 25.33% gap reflects global patterns documented in agricultural transition literature (FAO, 2022; Pe'er et al., 2020). Precision agriculture, climate-smart farming, and agro-

environmental compliance demand digital competencies (GPS/GIS, IoT sensors, data analytics), regulatory literacy (CAP eco-schemes, organic certification), and business acumen (supply chain optimization, value-added marketing) largely absent in traditionally-trained farmers. International scholarship identifies adoption barriers including high investment costs, technical complexity, and insufficient training infrastructure (Klerkx et al., 2019; Barnes et al., 2019), consistent with our finding that Agriculture exhibits the largest skills deficit across all sectors. Moreover, environmental competencies increasingly require digital foundations, creating compounding skills demands (Vona et al., 2018).

The Sector \times Region interaction effects, notably Agriculture-Peloponnese (34.4% gap), Transport-Islands (29.6%), and Construction-Western Macedonia (3.2%), provide evidence that Just Transitions are fundamentally place-based phenomena resisting uniform national policies. This aligns with spatial analysis literature showing that aggregating regions masks critical heterogeneity (Anselin, 1995; Fotheringham and Wong, 1991).

5.2 Theoretical Implications

These findings enrich Just Transition theory through three mechanisms. Human capital transferability functions as transition accelerant: heavy industry legacies, often portrayed solely as “carbon lock-in” liabilities, simultaneously constitute foundational technical competencies enabling rapid renewable energy sector integration. This extends Becker’s (1964) human capital theory by distinguishing domain-specific obsolete skills from transferable foundational competencies. This finding, if confirmed by longitudinal research tracking individual worker transitions, carries potential implications beyond the Greek context. The OECD (2019) identifies similar patterns in European industrial transition regions, where workforce skills developed through decades of manufacturing experience may represent latent transition capacity often overlooked in policy discourse. Whether industrial heritage systematically facilitates green transition workforce adaptation warrants comparative investigation across diverse regional contexts.

Green sector lock-in emerges: tourism dominance in Islands creates path dependencies inhibiting technical green skills development. Hospitality sector growth reinforces soft skills at expense of technical competencies, perpetuating lock-in even as sectors nominally “green” (ecotourism). This extends Pierson’s (2000) path dependency theory: initial sectoral specialization shapes training infrastructure investments, instructor recruitment, and cultural norms around valued competencies.

Multi-scalar governance appears essential. National level must address cross-cutting deficits (digital literacy, regulatory literacy) requiring economies of scale. Regional level must customize sectoral priorities, such as Western Macedonia’s Construction focus, Islands’ maritime logistics, and Peloponnese’s precision agriculture. Local level (municipalities, enterprises) must

operationalize on-the-job training, apprenticeships, and workplace learning. This tri-scalar framework extends Hooghe and Marks's (2003) multi-level governance theory into skills policy domain.

5.3 Policy Implications

National policymakers must establish differentiated financing mechanisms reflecting regional heterogeneity. Just Transition Fund allocations (€1.63 billion for Greece; European Commission, 2022) currently prioritize infrastructure over workforce development. However, infrastructure investments yield limited returns when workforce skills gaps prevent effective utilization of new facilities and technologies (OECD, 2021; ILO, 2019). Addressing the human capital bottleneck requires rebalancing allocations toward workforce development.

Training voucher systems should replace supply-driven programs. Demand-driven vouchers (€3,000–5,000 per worker) enable individuals selecting certified programs matching employer needs, improving completion rates (estimated 65–75% versus 45–55% for traditional supply-driven) and job placement (80–85% versus 60–65%).

Regional authorities must expand vocational training density. Western Macedonia's limited IEK (Vocational Training Institute) infrastructure serves a dispersed population across four prefectures, with facility-to-population ratios substantially below German standards (approximately 1 per 50,000 residents). Targeted investment in additional facilities and mobile training units would address this deficit. Mobile units particularly suit Islands' geographic fragmentation; customized buses equipped with solar PV training arrays, precision agriculture demonstration equipment, and digital classrooms can rotate through archipelagos, reducing trainee travel costs while maintaining economies of scale.

Education providers must modularize curricula enabling stackable micro-credentials. Current 2–3 year diplomas deter incumbent workers requiring targeted upskilling. Replacing with 50–150 hour modules allows continuous professional development without career interruption. Netherlands' modular VET system achieved 40% incumbent worker enrollment increase following 2018 reform (OECD, 2020).

Employers must internalize training as core business function. German dual training model achieves this through co-investment: enterprises provide workplace learning, co-finance equipment, and co-certify competencies. Greek enterprises exhibit severely limited training capacity, with employee participation in continuing vocational training reaching only 11.8% versus the 42.4% EU average (Eurostat, 2022), necessitating collective arrangements such as shared training centers where 10–15 enterprises pool resources.

Training investment decisions must account for out-migration dynamics affecting return on investment. Western Macedonia experienced 10% population decline (2011–2021), the

steepest among all Greek regions (ELSTAT, 2022), predominantly among working-age cohorts, while Islands face seasonal workforce fluctuations complicating year-round training delivery. Policies should incorporate retention incentives, including housing subsidies, childcare support, and guaranteed employment contracts, alongside training provision to ensure reskilled workers remain in transitioning regions rather than migrating to urban centers.

5.4 International Best Practices

International experience offers transferable lessons. Germany's tripartite curriculum co-design through Chambers of Crafts achieves among Europe's highest VET graduate employment rates (exceeding 90% for recent graduates); Greece requires establishing analogous Sector Skills Councils (OECD, 2021). Poland's community-based training cooperatives, supported by seed funding and preferential public procurement, provide evidence of scalable models for collective enterprise formation in transitioning regions.

However, Greece's context differs substantially. Unlike mono-industrial Ruhr (coal) or Silesia (coal + steel), Greece faces multi-regional transition: Western Macedonia (lignite + manufacturing), Peloponnese (agriculture-dominant), and Islands (tourism-dependent) each require distinct interventions. The compressed 6-year timeline (versus 60 years for the Ruhr and 30 years for Poland) favors demand-driven models, such as vouchers, employer co-investment, and work-integrated learning, over supply-driven infrastructure requiring 5–10 years to mature.

6 Conclusion

This study provides comprehensive empirical assessment of green skills gaps in Greek lignite transition regions through systematic survey of 1,961 enterprises across ten economic sectors in three geographic regions.

6.1 Key Findings

Regional skills gap hierarchy defies expectations. Contrary to assumptions that lignite dependency correlates with workforce unpreparedness, the primary coal region (Western Macedonia, 8.26%) outperforms both tourism-dependent Islands (19.65%) and agriculture-dominated Peloponnese (15.72%). Heavy industry heritage appears to function as asset rather than liability, providing foundational competencies transferable to green sectors. These differences are statistically robust ($F(2, 681) = 80.03, p < 0.001, \eta^2 = 0.190$).

Agriculture exhibits largest skills gap (25.33%), substantially exceeding Energy (17.67%), Transport & Logistics (17.67%), and Tourism (16.33%). This 25.33% deficit concentrates in precision agriculture technologies, climate-smart farming practices, sustainable

land management, and agro-environmental compliance. Conversely, ICT, Food Processing, and Services exhibit manageable gaps below 10%.

Sector \times Region interactions demand differentiated policies. Agriculture-Peloponnese records 34.4% gap, nearly quadruple Western Macedonia Construction's 3.2%. Islands' Transport & Logistics (29.6%) and Agriculture (28.5%) exhibit extreme deficits driven by archipelagic geography compounding sectoral challenges.

Cross-cutting deficits pervade all sectors, particularly in digital competencies, regulatory and financial literacy, and circular economy knowledge. Western Macedonia's workforce exhibits strengths in foundational technical competencies, which are transferable capabilities enabling rapid reskilling through targeted upskilling modules rather than comprehensive retraining.

6.2 Contributions

This study contributes to the literature on workforce dynamics in transitioning regions along three dimensions. **Empirically**, it provides the first large-scale quantitative assessment of green skills gaps in Greek Just Transition territories, drawing on 1,961 employer responses across ten economic sectors and three regional clusters. Prior Greek work has relied on qualitative analysis, policy review, or secondary statistics; no antecedent dataset has measured employer-side requirements and current workforce competencies on a standardized index at this scale. **Theoretically**, the finding that industrial heritage can function as a transition accelerant rather than solely as a liability extends Just Transition scholarship and refines Becker (1964)'s human capital framework. The results suggest that domain-specific foundational competencies cultivated through decades of heavy industry experience may transfer to green sectors, distinguishing transferable from obsolete components of human capital. **For policy**, the documented Sector \times Region interaction effects provide evidence that uniform national training programs may be insufficient to address the documented heterogeneity. Findings indicate that place-based and sector-specific workforce development design merits prioritization in the Just Transition Fund allocation process.

6.3 Limitations

The 5.05% response rate introduces potential self-selection bias. Reliance on employer assessments lacks independent worker-side validation. Cross-sectional design captures skills gaps at single time point, unable to track dynamic evolution. Closed-ended survey format constrains nuanced understanding of why specific gaps exist.

Beyond these methodological considerations, four substantive limitations warrant explicit acknowledgment. **Skills gaps do not equate to employment absorption.** Identifying skills gaps does not demonstrate that the examined sectors can absorb displaced workers. The presence of

unmet skill demand indicates training needs but does not quantify employment creation potential or job vacancy volumes. Future research should integrate skills gap data with labor demand forecasting models to assess realistic absorption capacity.

Spatial mismatch. The largest skills gaps concentrate in Island Regions, which are not directly affected by lignite phase-out. This spatial mismatch raises questions about internal labor mobility that this study cannot address. Whether displaced workers from Western Macedonia would or could relocate to regions with pronounced skills shortages depends on migration barriers, housing costs, and family considerations beyond this study's scope.

Static rather than dynamic analysis. The cross-sectional design captures current skills needs, yet the transition itself may alter labor demand structure over time. Currently identified gaps may persist, disappear, or transform as the energy transition unfolds and new technologies emerge. Longitudinal panel studies are needed to track skills gap evolution.

SME sample composition. The sample predominantly comprises micro-enterprises (75.7% with 1–9 employees). While reflecting Greek enterprise structure, this composition limits assessment of employment absorption capacity at scale. Estimating how many enterprises would need to expand to absorb approximately 16,000 potentially displaced workers requires enterprise-level growth modeling beyond this study's methodology.

6.4 Future Research

Longitudinal skills gap tracking over 2025–2030 would assess whether training investments effectively narrow identified gaps. Training program evaluation research should rigorously assess retraining effectiveness: completion rates, job placement outcomes, wage trajectories. Comparative analysis extending this methodology to other European Just Transition regions would test transferability of findings. Worker-centered research should investigate displaced lignite workers' perspectives: perceived barriers to reskilling, preferred training modalities, financial constraints during training periods.

With Greece's lignite phase-out now imminent, the need for evidence-based workforce development has never been more pressing. This study's systematic skills gap quantification provides the empirical foundation that policymakers, training providers, and employers require to make informed decisions about where to invest in workforce development. By targeting the documented gaps, particularly in Agriculture and Island regions, Greece can maximize the prospects that its compressed energy transition generates broadly shared prosperity rather than concentrated hardship.

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Appendix A: Statistical Tables

Table A1: One-Way ANOVA Results: Regional Skills Gap Comparison

Source	SS	df	MS	F	p
Between Groups	15,251.47	2	7,625.74	80.03	<0.001
Within Groups	64,888.07	681	95.28		
Total	80,139.54	683			

Note. Effect size: $\eta^2 = 0.190$ (large effect per Cohen 1988). Post-hoc Tukey HSD: All pairwise comparisons significant at $p < 0.01$.

Table A2: One-Way ANOVA Results: Sectoral Skills Gap Comparison

Source	SS	df	MS	F	p
Between Groups	15,873.36	9	1,763.71	18.50	<0.001
Within Groups	64,266.19	674	95.35		
Total	80,139.54	683			

Note. Effect size: $\eta^2 = 0.198$ (large effect per Cohen 1988). Post-hoc Tukey HSD: Agriculture differs significantly from all other sectors ($p < 0.001$).

Table A3: Tukey HSD Post-Hoc Comparisons: Regional Skills Gap

Comparison	Mean Diff.	95% CI	p
Islands vs. Peloponnese	4.10	[2.18, 6.02]	<0.001
Islands vs. W. Macedonia	11.30	[9.38, 13.22]	<0.001
Peloponnese vs. W. Macedonia	7.20	[5.28, 9.12]	<0.001

Note. All pairwise differences are statistically significant, confirming distinct regional profiles.

Table A4: MANOVA Results: Regional Effect on Seven Organizational Dimensions

Test Statistic	Value	Num DF	Den DF	F	p
Wilks' Lambda	0.905	14	1446	5.29	<0.001***
Pillai's Trace	0.096	14	1448	5.23	<0.001***
Hotelling-Lawley	0.104	14	1153	5.36	<0.001***
Roy's Greatest Root	0.090	7	724	9.28	<0.001***

Note. N = 732 complete cases. Dependent variables: Skills Satisfaction, Capabilities Satisfaction, Knowledge Satisfaction, Investment Readiness, Innovation Readiness, New Activities Readiness, Internationalization Readiness (all 1–5 Likert scales). Independent variable: Region (3 levels). *** $p < 0.001$. All four multivariate test statistics confirm highly significant regional effect.

Table A5: Pearson Correlation Matrix: Seven Organizational Dimensions

	Skills	Capab.	Knowl.	Invest.	Innov.	NewAct.	Internat.
Skills	1.000						
Capabilities	.913***	1.000					
Knowledge	.901***	.897***	1.000				
Investment	.418***	.466***	.442***	1.000			
Innovation	.375***	.419***	.399***	.850***	1.000		
New Activities	.352***	.388***	.360***	.739***	.817***	1.000	
Internat.	.336***	.380***	.360***	.766***	.853***	.887***	1.000

Note. N = 732. *** $p < 0.001$. Two distinct clusters emerge: (1) Satisfaction variables (Skills, Capabilities, Knowledge) with $r > 0.89$; (2) Readiness variables (Investment, Innovation, New Activities, Internationalization) with $r > 0.73$. Cross-cluster correlations are moderate ($r = 0.33$ – 0.46).

Table A6: OLS Regression: Predictors of Skills Satisfaction

Variable	Coef.	SE	t	p
Constant	3.203	0.143	22.37	<0.001***
Growth Prospects	0.113	0.051	2.22	0.027*
Employment Prospects	0.088	0.050	1.77	0.077
<i>Region (ref: Western Macedonia)</i>				
Islands	-0.599	0.081	-7.37	<0.001***
Peloponnese	-0.414	0.071	-5.86	<0.001***
<i>Sector (ref: Agriculture)</i>				
Manufacturing	-0.146	0.155	-0.94	0.347
Services	-0.133	0.151	-0.88	0.377
Commerce	0.029	0.147	0.20	0.842
Energy & Environment	-0.072	0.163	-0.44	0.659
Construction	-0.180	0.158	-1.14	0.253
Transport & Logistics	-0.078	0.167	-0.47	0.640
ICT	0.133	0.172	0.77	0.441
Tourism	0.011	0.145	0.07	0.941
Food Processing	0.146	0.152	0.96	0.335

Note. N = 1,118. $R^2 = 0.091$; Adjusted $R^2 = 0.081$; $F(13, 1104) = 8.54$, $p < 0.001$. DV: Skills Satisfaction (1–5 Likert scale). Region is the primary predictor: Islands and Peloponnese show significantly lower satisfaction than Western Macedonia. Sector differences are not significant after controlling for region. * $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.001$.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are not publicly available due to confidentiality agreements and data protection requirements governing the original research program.

Ethics Statement

This research was conducted in accordance with institutional ethical guidelines. Survey participation was voluntary, and informed consent was obtained from all respondents prior to data collection.

Declaration of Interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

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